

Sustainability Standards As A Cultural Behavior For the Product Designers

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 05, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 08, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Environment Protection, Emissions, The Culture Approach; Conventional Design, Open Systems, Users' Experience</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5768422</p>	<p><i>Products are a significant source of emissions and environmental pollution. Sustainability is the logical solution to solve that problem by reshaping human relationships towards the natural world. Moving from environmentally friendly products to higher levels of integrated sustainability requires a new design thinking based on ethical basics and deep cooperation. So, products must carry new emotional, cultural values and technological advantages to be accepted by the consumers. Companies are still producing huge, cheaper, faster quantities without regard for their environmental effects. A fundamental shift must happen in the design ideas by changing the designers' culture to achieve open systems theory and stay out of current closed systems that harm the environment. That has happened for many centuries since the first industrial revolution until now. So this paper presents a new vision in the relationship of different design aspects to the environment to identify the sustainability strategies to be an integral part of the designers' cultural approach and thinking for new products.</i></p>

Introduction

Since the late twentieth century, environmental problems have become global in scope. The energy crises of the 1970s demonstrated the extent to which the international community had become dependent on non-renewable energy resources.[1] There is a growing global awareness of the danger of human-caused global warming in the twenty-first century, mainly happened by various emissions. Sustainability from the environmental point means continuity despite the transformation from one shape to another without a definite end. It has cultural, social, and economic meanings. In the field of products design, sustainability refers to that; products achieve the complete functions in the lowest range of consumption and emission of different energies and raw materials, with the possibility of transforming from one structure to another to perform new previously planned tasks during the design process.[2] Therefore, a global trend became a fact towards applying sustainability principles in all industrial and economic aspects.[3]

In light of the race towards products marketing and attracting customers' attention, the designers and companies still deal with the issue of sustainability as a secondary goal. However, this wrong vision can be modified by developing the design strategies in different institutes so that the environmental factors will be in front of design consideration. So the design theory must change from the user-centered design to the environment-centered design, as the environment contains products and consumers together.[4] Seeking to change the life cycle of products into a new phase of use once the first phase of service is over, representing the core of applying sustainability standards in reducing waste and increasing value.

1-Sustainability in design

Sustainable design is much more to be addressed as an environmental design, eco-design, environmentally conscious design, green design, etc. In general, sustainability is the philosophy of designing physical objects, the built environment, and services to comply with social, economic, and ecological sustainability principles.[5]

The sustainable designed product has its continuous life cycle, which changes from one state to another without alimited end.[6]

The goal of good design is not only to enhance its aesthetics and appearance. But to operate within a set of social, cultural, and ethical values. Moreover, sustainable design must consider the systems and relationships in which the products are generated. Therefore, it is important to sketch out and plan the flow of materials from one system to another in a whole relation. [7]

The sustainable design aims to eliminate any negative environmental impact through skillful, sensitive, and planned design for use and after the finishing of the life cycle. Sustainable design requires renewable resources that impact the environment minimally and connect people with the natural environment. Beyond the

"elimination of negative environmental impact," sustainable design must create meaningful innovations and modify human behavior. A dynamic balance between economy and society is intended to generate long-term relationships between user and object/service and be respectful and mindful of environmental and social differences.[8]

Sustainable design is also about creating a new production system in which all the industrial cycles are open and connected. The flow of materials and energy resources can be incorporated together so that all wastes must be reused.[9]

So, the conversion from conventional to sustainable product design can be a fact through improvements such as Clients' aspirations, companies strategy, users behavior, and new designers' cultural approach.[10]

2- Products as a source of environmental pollution

Product design is about creating an object. And to be commercially successful, its physical presence and symbolic meaning need to fit the industrial aims economically, whether this object is a car, a mobile phone, a kitchen gadget, or a T.V. set.[11]

Product Design also is the professional service of creating and developing concepts and specifications that optimize the function, value, and appearance for the mutual benefit of both user and manufacturer. The role of industrial designers is to create design solutions for problems of form, usability, ergonomics, marketing, etc. Sometimes they focus only on the relationship of form and function without regard to the environmental considerations, which may come at the last of their priorities.[12]

The current design education commonly contains courses that encourage exploring relations of weight, structure, composition, size, shape, material, etc. Historically, the first Bauhaus in Germany established the education programs from 1919 to 1933 and subsequently refined by the New Bauhaus in Chicago in 1937. [13] Although later the design education philosophy has developed from one country to another, and the design process has changed from product-centered design to user-centered design, this means that; the user has the priority in the design process, as shown in figure (1).

Figure (1) shows the classic product design process

Since the previous design process did not prioritize the environment, many product residues will be dumped into the external environment after their lifespan, becoming a real source of pollution. These pollutants will be a part of the sources that affect the environment, as shown in figure(2)

Figure (2) shows the wastes of conventional products as a source of environmental pollution

3-Sustainability standards in product design

Through many experiments, it was possible to reach a set of standards that can be applied during the innovative design process that can achieve sustainability for the design, and these standards will not be able to be applied by designers on their own if they do not become part of the design education strategy worldwide and are accepted by manufacturers as well as consumers, as follows: -

-Easiness to disassemble the product

During their study and practice of the design process, designers must be trained to have a strategy for dismantling the components of a product into discrete parts that are reusable or, at worst, recyclable. This action will make sustainability easier. [14]

- Reduce the number of materials and parts in the product

When the designer sets sustainability criteria in mind during the design process, he reduces the number of materials, colors, etc., used in the composition of the product to reach one material if possible, and this will save a lot of effort in the dismantling and recycling processes, as shown in figure (3)

Figure shows

cardboard and monocolored products

-Reduce the weight of materials

It is vital to save the weight and thickness of the raw materials of the products while determining the final specifications of the product at the end of the design process, without damaging the duties of performing the specified functions. Such suggestion will be an influential factor in facilitating the recycling of the product after its consumption. Furthermore, it will save a lot of energy consumed in recycling operations. Therefore, this reduction has a double advantage, helping to protect resources and reduce harmful emissions. [15]

-Reuse of the products' components

Repurposing the parts of the product after the end of its life is one of the most critical sustainability standards, which requires the designer to have a particular methodology during the design process to make a vision for each part of the reuse after the product's consumption. [15]

Figure (4) shows repurposed of the used product parts

-Minimizing the product's volume

Product miniaturization is one of the design trends that emerged in the last century. Still, it has come back in the modern era to implement sustainability standards, as shown in figure (5).

The application of reducing the size of the products will provide in the following:-

- Saving the amount of consumed raw materials.
- Increasing the spaces inside homes and various places.
- Reducing the consumed energy in recycling processes.
- Reduce product cost.
- protect Environmen from various industrial used components.

Figure (5) shows minimizing the volume in products

-maintainability

When designers develop their perceptions of products, they must consider facilitating maintenance procedures, which increases the product's useful life. In addition, reducing consumption will protect the environment.[17]

-Usingecofuel

Using biological and renewable energies with modern technological ideas will create high-level products with sustainable specifications to achieve environmental goals.

4-Discussions and results

By presenting the previous studies and analyses, it seems clear that the great challenge to achieving sustainability in products design and protecting the environment is to make sustainability part of the usual design process and be a cultural behavior of the product designers.

By incorporating the environmental considerations in the design process will significantly contribute to solving this problem. Zero emissions can be obtained through good planning from the product designers, companies, and users of these products. So we have three strategies to help in solving this problem, they can be explained as follows:-

-Companies legalizations

Designing for sustainability should be part of the company's policy. It will be achieved through a comprehensive approach of legislation that encourages designers to think of sustainable solutions. These innovations can replace old solutions in existing products or represent new solutions in product development processes.

Also, companies should encourage scientific research in critical areas such as environmentally friendly materials and saving products' energy consumption using renewable energy sources such as solar energy and biofuels. Monitoring rewards for sustainable design will also encourage everyone to take on these experiences. And finally, by granting the companies which apply sustainability more competitive advantages in markets.

-Users experience

Users' behavior and experience can be improved towards the environment by applying the following:-

- reducing different consumption rates.

- Achieving the environmental requirements during the products' use.

- proper disposal of the products or their parts at the end of their life span.

- Studying the users' behavior as the social part towards sustainability, such as; what people do, why, when, where and how they do it, who they do it with, will increase the rate of sustainable solutions.

The study of users' behavior will push the design's locality to improve all the sustainable problems. So designers can make good green behavior easy as follows:-

- Making parts easier to clean and repair, which will reduce throwing them away quickly.

- working on the idea of emotionally durable design. It shows that "how things are made can affect how we value them."

- Removing the barriers to sustainable behavior by researching with people and in everyday contexts to find out what the barriers are and treat them directly.

-Modifying the cultural designers' behavior

To prepare the product design students to deal with the sustainability complex problems, they need to be provided with an educational program with a sustainability context. And the traditional academic programs must be improved because sustainability education is concerned with new topics such as cognition, attitudes, emotions, skills, ethical and spiritual convictions. Therefore, they do not need only knowledge to generate practical design solutions, but also they need intellectual development and awareness to understand the impact of their design decisions.

So it is essential to apply the following rules to change the students' culture towards sustainability:-

- sustainability must be a part of the product design's students' everyday thinking.

- Sustainability education needs to be incorporated into the core curricula of many design disciplines.

- The courses which focus on sustainable development must include an emphasis on the social context of sustainability.

- Students must be educated to investigate how their decisions will influence the systems which they design.

- The sustainable changes must be accompanied by valid assessment to ensure that the objectives are being achieved.

- In sustainable design, the outputs from one step become inputs to another one.

Conclusions

- Sustainability is a societal thought and not just an individual endeavor.

- The sustainability of products is an essential part of protecting the environment from a pollution's source.

- Designers' thinking towards sustainability can be developed by changing their culture of thinking methods and habits.

- Changing the current study programs is an essential factor in the drive towards sustainability.

- Sustainability principles should be applied in more affluent countries to encourage poorer countries to do the same.

- Elements of the sustainability approach include agencies, organizations, companies, designers, and consumers.

Recommendations

The research objectives and previous results are achieved by applying the following recommendations:-

- Sustainability is a societal thought, and therefore it must be focused on in the media and social networking sites.

- Encouraging manufacturers and producers towards sustainability from the beginning of the design process to production and external marketing.

- Presenting international competitions and awards for the best sustainable designs annually.

- Develop product design education curricula so that sustainability becomes the dominant thought in the design process

- Develop societal legislation that protects the environment from resulting pollution from various industries and products.

-Holding endless meetings at the global level to discuss the environmental situation of the globe and take firm steps to reduce environmental damage.

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